

EMPOWERED TEACHERS: LEVEL OF GENDER AND DEVELOPMENT AWARENESS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS FOR ENHANCED FACULTY EMPOWERMENT

Floro T. del Pilar III, MEM and Evangeline T. Abillon

Guinayang National High School, San Mateo, Rizal, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11393199>

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to investigate the level of awareness of Guinayang National High School teachers about Gender and Development concepts and principles as well as their perceptions on integrating gender and development in their classes. The researchers, as part of the school's technical working group on GAD, will use this study as basis for the identification of topics to be given on any GAD seminar or symposium for the teachers. Moreover, the DepEd Order no. 32, s. 2017 or the Gender Responsive Basic Education Policy mandated that DepEd be committed to integrating principles of gender equality, equity, sensitivity, non-discrimination, and human rights in the governance of basic education. This is best achieved if the teachers are well-equipped with knowledge about GAD. Employing a quantitative descriptive method, the mean and standard deviations are used for level of awareness and perceptions while Mann Whitney U-Test and Kruskal Wallis H-Test are used to identify any differences in the level of awareness and perception of the respondents. The study found that the teachers have 'good awareness with clear understanding' of the GAD concepts and principles and they 'agree' that GAD must be integrated in their teaching. Results also show that there are no significant differences in their level of awareness and perception when they are grouped according to gender, age, designation, and highest educational attainment. A capacity-building program for teachers was developed as an output of this study.

Keywords: *GAD, Awareness, GAD Integration, GNHS, Teachers*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is mandated by international and national laws to include gender equality into its educational principles, objectives, and methods. Article XIV, Section 1 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution mandates the state to safeguard and enhance the right of all people to quality education at all levels and to ensure education is accessible to everyone. The Government of the Republic of the Philippines (GRP) has pledged to adhere to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women. RA No. 10533 mandates the Department of Education (DepEd) to ensure that the basic education curriculum is responsive to gender and culture (Rule II, Section 10.2).

This study assessed the current level of gender and development awareness among the teachers at Guinayang National High School. High school teachers have a key role in shaping attitudes towards gender and societal advancement. This research is essential for evaluating the impact of Gender and Development programs on addressing gender disparities. The researcher aims to detect any shortcomings in the teachers' awareness. This research will identify certain domains that can provide valuable insights for improved planning related to GAD, enabling instructors to better understand GAD principles. The researcher seeks to significantly contribute to creating a more inclusive school by utilizing the transformative potential of an integrated gender and development program. This is the same aim of Pedrajas and Jalandoni (2023) when they found out that discrimination and a lack of gender knowledge are barriers to achieving gender equality.

Gender inequities continue to exist inside educational institutions, regardless of legislative frameworks. In the study of Abulencia et al. (2023), they discovered bullying and microaggressions by students and teachers as well as gender biases, gender blindness, and inadequate infrastructure to support a gender-responsive learning environment. Hemillan-Sacro et al. (2022) revealed that in their Division, the DepEd's level of gender mainstreaming is still in the foundation formation stage or stage 1. In the study of Villagrancia (2023), he found that the challenges in the implementation of GAD programs in their local school are limited resource speakers, irresponsive stakeholders, insufficient training, and lack of support from organizations.

This research will investigate if the GAD programs provide adequate services, which could be a factor in the discrepancies reported. Eliminate stereotypes and gender biases from the classroom. It is essential to assess whether teachers are aware of and understand GAD issues, as they have a significant impact on forming the attitudes of future generations. The main goal of this research is to gather empirical data to inform Gender and Development (GAD) programmes while adhering to ideals of development and gender equality.

Research Questions

This research explored the awareness of gender and development concepts, and the perception of gender and development integration in the instruction of the teachers of Guinayang National High School for the school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, this research answered the following questions.

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. designation;
 - 1.4. department; and
 - 1.5. education?
2. What is the level of awareness of gender and development concepts of the respondents?
3. What is the perception of the respondents about the gender and development integration in instruction?
4. Is there any significant difference in the level of awareness and the perception of the respondents on gender and development concepts when they are grouped according to their profile?
5. What faculty capacity building program can be drafted according to the result of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized the quantitative research method which is defined by Daniel and Cross (2018) as a study design which entails gathering numerical data to depict a certain occurrence or population without altering any variables. This research kind tries to offer a current overview or features of the issue being studied. The design made appropriate and precise interpretations of the gathered data with the use of statistical methods.

Research Respondents

The researchers used the Cochran formula to get the sample size of the population. There are 64 teachers in Guinayang National High School and the computed sample size is 55. A stratified sampling technique was used so that teachers from all departments were well-represented in this study. To keep the ethical considerations on agreed consent, the researchers chose to give the questionnaire only to those who gave their consent.

Data Collection

The researchers made use of the Gender and Development Awareness and Perception Survey Questionnaire by Villanueva (2019). The researchers adapted the questionnaire to the context of the teachers of Guinayang National High School and had it validated by the experts. The questionnaire was pilot tested to teachers who did not take part in the study. The Cronbach's alpha was used to test its reliability and it yielded .944 which is verbally interpreted as excellent. The questionnaire was converted into a google form and was sent to the teachers through the school's official GC. The respondents' responses were automatically retrieved and exported to Microsoft Excel.

Data Analysis

After importing all information from the respondents, the researcher used the following statistical treatment of data:

- To present the profiles of the respondents, frequency and percentage were used.
- To present the level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts, the mean and standard deviation were used.
- To present the perception about gender and development integration in instruction, the mean and standard deviation were used.
- To test for significant differences in the level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts as well as the perception about gender and development integration when the respondents are grouped according to profile, the non-parametric statistical tools Mann-Whitney U-Test and Kruskal Wallis H-Test were used.

RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

1. The Profile of the Respondents

Table 1: Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	46	83.6
Male	9	16.4
Total	55	100

Table 1 presents the gender profile of the respondents. It shows that majority of the teaching personnel of Guinayang National High School are female. Regalado (2017) informed that there are more female than males both in the public and private high schools because teaching is a female-dominated profession.

Table 2: Age

Age Group	Frequency	Percent
51 and older	8	14.5
41-50	26	47.3
31-40	16	29.1
20-30	5	9.1
Total	55	100

Table 2 shows the distribution of respondents according to age. Almost half of the respondents fall within the range of 41-50 years old while the lowest percentage of 9.1% represented the youngest age group.

Table 3: Designation

Designation	Frequency	Percent
Teacher III	8	14.5
Teacher I	47	85.5
Total	55	100

Table 3 shows the distribution of respondents according to their respective designation where 85.5% are Teacher 1 while 14.5% are Teacher III.

Table 4: Department

Department	Frequency	Percent
AP	9	16.4
TLE	8	14.5
Math	8	14.5
Science	8	14.5
Filipino	8	14.5
EsP	6	10.9
MAPEH	4	7.3
English	4	7.3
Total	55	100

Table 4 shows that there are equal numbers of respondents from the department of TLE, Math, Science and Filipino with equal percentage of 14.5, while 16.4% were from AP, 10.9% from EsP, and 7.3% from MAPEH and English Departments. All departments are represented in this study.

Table 5 : Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Doctor's Degree Earner/Graduate	2	3.6
Master's Degree Earner/Graduate	28	50.9
Certificate in Professional Education	4	7.3
Bachelor in Secondary Education	21	38.2
Total	55	100.0

Table 5 shows the distribution of the respondents based on their Highest Educational Attainment. Only 3.6% or 2 of the respondents earned or graduated Doctoral degree while 50.9% or 28 have earned or finished Masteral degree. 7.3% or 4 with

certificate in Professional Education and 38.2% or 21 have Bachelor Degree in Secondary Education.

2. The Level of Awareness and Understanding of Gender and Development Concepts

Table 7: Level of Awareness of Gender and Development

Concepts	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Gender Equality	4.14	.84	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Gender Identity	4.10	.76	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Gender Roles	4.01	.78	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Gender and Development	3.92	.79	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Gender Equity	3.90	.90	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Gender Needs	3.89	.85	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Women in Development	3.87	.88	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Gender Sensitive	3.81	.88	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Women and Development	3.81	.96	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Gender Integration	3.72	.98	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Practical Gender Needs	3.65	.90	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Gender Analysis	3.63	1.00	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Gender Mainstreaming	3.54	.89	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding
Strategic Gender Needs	3.47	.89	Partial Awareness with Some Understanding
Overall Mean	3.82	.75	Good Awareness with Clear Understanding

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Completely Unaware; 1.51-2.50 Limited Awareness; 2.51-3.50 Partial Awareness with Some Understanding; 3.51-4.50 Good Awareness with Clear Understanding; and 4.51-5.00 Comprehensive Awareness with Deep Understanding

Table 7 presents that the respondents generally exhibit a high level of awareness regarding various gender and development concepts. The mean scores for all but one concept fall within the range of 3.51 to 4.50, which indicates "Good Awareness with Clear Understanding." The concepts Gender Equality (mean = 4.14, SD = 0.84), Gender Identity (mean = 4.10, SD = 0.76), and Gender Roles (mean = 4.01, SD = 0.78) are at the higher end of this range. The relatively low standard deviations imply consistent levels of understanding among the teachers surveyed.

However, the concept 'Strategic Gender Needs' (mean = 3.47, SD = 0.89) has a mean score that falls within the "Partial Awareness with Some Understanding" range. This is a notable gap in their comprehension of strategic gender needs. Moreover, some concepts such as Gender Mainstreaming (mean = 3.54, SD = 0.89) and Gender Analysis (mean = 3.63, SD = 1.00) also have slightly lower scores and higher standard deviations, indicating a less consistent and slightly lower level of understanding compared to other concepts. Regardless, the overall teachers' level of awareness and understanding of GAD Concepts has a verbal interpretation of 'Good Awareness with Clear Understanding'. This is aligned with the study of Cabillo-Jimenez (2021) which concluded that the teachers are aware and knowledgeable about Gender and Development concepts and issues in schools.

3. The Perception About Gender and Development Integration in Instruction

Table 8: Perception About Gender and Development Integration in Instruction

Indicator	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Gender and Development Integration in Education is relevant in the Philippines	4.10	.91	Agree
Gender and Development Integration in Education is timely	4.05	.84	Agree
I would like to integrate Gender and Development into my instruction	4.14	.80	Agree
I am integrating Gender and Development in my instruction	3.83	.99	Agree
I would like to know more about Gender and Development	4.05	.84	Agree
I would like to know more on how to integrate GAD to my instruction	4.32	.79	Agree
It is possible to integrate GAD to my instruction	4.30	.79	Agree
Every teacher should integrate GAD in their instruction	4.12	.81	Agree
There is always a way to integrate GAD in the instruction	4.23	.74	Agree
GAD in education should be a concern for all teachers, male and female alike	4.30	.79	Agree
Overall Mean	4.15	.69	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree; 1.51-2.50 Disagree; 2.51-3.50 Neutral; 3.51-4.50 Agree; and 4.51-5.00 Strongly Agree

Table 8 reveals that the respondents have a positive perception of integrating Gender and Development (GAD) concepts into their instruction. The mean scores for all the items fall within the range of 3.51 to 4.50, which corresponds to "Agree." This indicates that teachers recognize the relevance and timeliness of GAD integration in education as reflected in the mean scores of 4.10 (SD = 0.91) and 4.05 (SD = 0.84) respectively. Teachers also express a strong personal interest in incorporating GAD into their teaching, with high mean scores for items such as "I would like to integrate Gender and Development into my instruction" (mean = 4.14, SD = 0.80) and "I am integrating Gender and Development in my instruction" (mean = 3.83, SD = 0.99).

Furthermore, the table shows a strong willingness among teachers to learn more about GAD and its integration into instruction. The overall mean score of 4.15 (SD = 0.69) suggests that teachers believe in the importance of GAD in education, emphasizing that GAD integration should be a concern for all teachers. This is aligned with the study of Talon et al. (2020) which highlighted how teachers prioritized establishing a classroom atmosphere that is considerate of gender and tackling gender discrimination.

4. The Significant Difference in the Level of Awareness and the Perception of the Respondents on Gender and Development Concepts when they are Grouped According to their Profile

Table 9: Mann-Whitney U Test: Differences in the Level of Awareness and Understanding of Gender and Development Concepts and Perception of Gender and Development Integration in Instruction When Grouped According to Gender

Indicator	Gender	Mean	P-Value	Decision	Remarks
Level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts	Female	3.86	.568	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Male	3.63			
Perception of Gender and development Integration in Instruction	Female	4.10	.263	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Male	4.37			

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 9 indicates that there are no statistically significant differences in the level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts, nor in the perception of gender and development integration in instruction, when comparing male and female teachers. The mean score for female teachers' awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts is 3.86, while for male teachers it is 3.63. Despite the difference in mean scores, the p-value of 0.568 indicates that this difference is not statistically significant, thus the failure to reject the null hypothesis (Ho). This suggests that both male and female teachers have similar levels of awareness and understanding regarding gender and development concepts.

Similarly, the perception of gender and development integration in instruction also shows no significant difference between genders. Female teachers have a mean perception score of 4.10, and male teachers have a slightly higher mean score of 4.37. However, with a p-value of 0.263, this difference is not statistically significant. The decision to fail to reject the null hypothesis again indicates that both male and female teachers share similar views on the relevance and importance of integrating gender and development concepts into their teaching practices.

Table 10: Kruskal Wallis Test: Differences in the Level of Awareness and Understanding of Gender and Development Concepts and Perception of Gender and Development Integration in Instruction When Grouped According to Age Group

Indicator	Age Group	Mean	P-Value	Decision	Remarks
Level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts	20-30 yrs. old	4.28	.165	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40 yrs. old	3.53			
	41-50 yrs. old	3.85			
	51 and older	4.02			
Perception of Gender and development Integration in Instruction	20-30 yrs. old	4.46	.575	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40 yrs. old	3.93			
	41-50 yrs. old	4.15			
	51 and older	4.25			

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 10 presents that there is no significant differences in the level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts, as well as the perception of gender and development integration in instruction, across different age groups. The results show that the mean scores for the level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts vary among the age groups, but the p-value of 0.165 indicates that these differences are not statistically significant, leading to the decision to fail to reject the null hypothesis (Ho). This suggests that age does not significantly affect teachers' awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts.

Similarly, the perception of gender and development integration in instruction also shows no significant differences across age groups. The p-value of 0.575 shows that the differences are not statistically significant. The decision to fail to reject the null hypothesis again suggests that the perception of integrating gender and development concepts into instruction is consistently positive across all age groups. Overall, these findings imply that age does not play a significant role in influencing the teachers' awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts or their perception of the importance of integrating these concepts into their teaching.

Table 11: Mann-Whitney U Test: Differences in the Level of Awareness and Understanding of Gender and Development Concepts and Perception of Gender and Development Integration in Instruction When Grouped According to Designation

Indicator	Designation	Mean	P-Value	Decision	Remarks
Level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts	Teacher 1	3.86	.404	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 3	3.60			
Perception of Gender and development Integration in Instruction	Teacher 1	4.12	.503	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 3	4.28			

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 11 shows that there are no significant differences in the level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts, as well as the perception of gender and development integration in instruction, between teachers with different designations, specifically Teacher 1 and Teacher 3. The p-value of 0.404 indicates that the difference between teacher 1 and teacher 3 are not statistically significant. As a result, the null hypothesis (Ho) is not rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference in the awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts between Teacher 1 and Teacher 3.

In the same manner, the perception of gender and development integration in instruction shows a p-value of 0.503 which indicates that there is no statistically significant

difference between teachers 1 and 3. Therefore, the null hypothesis is again not rejected, suggesting that both Teacher 1 and Teacher 3 have similar perceptions regarding the integration of gender and development concepts into their instruction. Thus, the designation of teachers does not significantly influence their level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts, nor their perception of integrating these concepts into their educational practices.

Table 12: Kruskal Wallis Test: Differences in the Level of Awareness and Understanding of GAD Concepts and Perception of GAD Integration in Instruction When Grouped According to Department

Indicator	Department	Mean	P-Value	Decision	Remarks
Level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts	English	3.10	.176	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Filipino	4.33			
	Science	3.89			
	Math	3.74			
	AP	3.60			
	EsP	3.70			
	TLE	3.78			
	MAPEH	4.32			
Perception of Gender and development Integration in Instruction	English	3.90	.136	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Filipino	4.20			
	Science	4.41			
	Math	4.10			
	AP	4.57			
	EsP	3.81			
	TLE	3.68			
	MAPEH	4.25			

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 12 shows that there are no significant differences in the level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts, as well as the perception of gender and development integration in instruction, across different departments. Despite the variations in mean scores, the p-value of 0.176 indicates that these differences are not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho) is not rejected, suggesting that the teachers' department does not significantly affect their awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts.

Likewise, the perception of gender and development integration in instruction also shows variability across departments, but with a p-value of 0.136, these differences are not statistically significant, leading to the decision to fail to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that teachers' perceptions of integrating gender and development concepts into instruction are not significantly influenced by their department. Overall, these findings indicate that the subject the respondents teach does not play a significant role in shaping their awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts or their perceptions regarding the integration of these concepts into educational practices.

Table 13: Kruskal Wallis Test: Differences in the Level of Awareness and Understanding of Gender and Development Concepts and Perception of Gender and Development Integration in Instruction When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Indicator	Highest Educational Attainment	Mean	P-Value	Decision	Remarks
Level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts	Bachelor in Secondary Education	4.10	.141	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Certificate in Professional Education	4.23			
	Master's Degree Earner/Graduate	3.61			
	Doctor's Degree Earner/Graduate	4.00			
Perception of Gender and development Integration in Instruction	Bachelor in Secondary Education	4.10	.409	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Certificate in Professional Education	4.30			
	Master's Degree Earner/Graduate	4.10			
	Doctor's Degree Earner/Graduate	4.90			

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 13 indicates that there are no significant differences in the level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts, and the perception of gender and development integration in instruction, when grouped according to highest educational attainment. The the p-value of 0.141 indicates that the variations of means are not statistically significant, leading to the decision to fail to reject the null hypothesis (Ho). This suggests that the highest educational attainment does not significantly impact the level of awareness and understanding of gender and development concepts among the teachers.

Likewise, the perception of gender and development integration in instruction shows variability across different educational attainments but the p-value of 0.409 indicates that there are no statistically significant differences between the highest educational attainment groups. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected, suggesting that teachers' perceptions of integrating gender and development concepts into instruction are not significantly influenced by their highest educational attainment.

5. What faculty capacity building program can be drafted according to the result of the study?

The study reveals that while secondary school teachers generally have good awareness and understanding of Gender and Development (GAD) concepts, certain areas like Strategic Gender Needs (mean = 3.47, SD = 0.89), Gender Mainstreaming (mean = 3.54, SD = 0.89), and Gender Analysis (mean = 3.63, SD = 1.00) show lower

levels of comprehension. These areas have been identified as needing improvement due to their lower mean scores and, in some cases, higher standard deviations, indicating less consistent understanding among teachers. To address these gaps, a targeted faculty capacity building program should focus on enhancing teachers' knowledge and skills in these specific areas. This is in line with the proposal of Cagang (2023) on an introduction of a Pedagogy Program to improve GAD awareness and encourage the use of gender-sensitive teaching methods.

The proposed program could include specialized workshops and training sessions that delve deeply into Strategic Gender Needs, Gender Mainstreaming, and Gender Analysis. These sessions should use practical examples and case studies to illustrate the concepts and their applications in the classroom. Additionally, providing continuous professional development opportunities and resources, such as online modules, mentorship programs, and resource kits, can help sustain and deepen teachers' understanding. By focusing on these lower-scoring concepts, the program aims to elevate the overall level of GAD awareness and ensure that all teachers have a comprehensive understanding of these critical areas, thereby improving their ability to integrate GAD concepts effectively into their instruction.

Conclusions

The results show that the level of awareness and understanding of Gender and Development concepts is verbally interpreted as 'Good Awareness with Clear Understanding'. On their perception about Gender and Development Integration in Instruction, their overall mean is verbally interpreted as 'Agree'. Moreover, there is no statistically significant difference between the level of awareness and perception among the respondents when they are grouped according to their profiles. Thus, although the study reveals that teachers generally have good awareness and understanding of GAD, concepts such as strategic gender needs, gender mainstreaming, and gender analysis show lower mean so these topics should be targeted for faculty capacity building programs.

Recommendations

In light of the findings, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. Utilize the findings of the study in deciding for the topics and themes on GAD that should be enriched through seminars and workshops for the next school year.
2. Seminar/Workshop in the integration of GAD concepts in the curriculum and classroom practices.
3. A review of the curriculum for secondary schools must be conducted so that GAD integration may be ensured.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study followed the ethical guidelines for conducting research with the teacher respondents. Before commencing the data collection process, the researcher made certain that informed consent was acquired from the teachers. Only those who consented responded to the questionnaire. The participants were provided with information regarding the study's objective, the utilization of the data, and the voluntary aspect of their involvement. In addition, the participants' information was ensured to be confidential, and any identifiable data was eliminated during the data processing phase to safeguard their privacy.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank the Research Committee of the Guinayang National High School for the guidance in the conduct and completion of this study. The SDS of the Division of Rizal, the PSDS of the District of San Mateo, and the School Head of Guinayang National High School where the study was conducted are also acknowledged for taking part in this academic endeavor. Special acknowledgment to the families of the authors who provided support and inspiration in the conduct of this study.

REFERENCES

- Abulencia, A., Hibanada, R., Bedural, Z., Dellomos, C., & Aggarao, M. (2023). A Qualitative Cross-Sectional Study on Gender Issues in the Schools Division of Marikina: Basis for GAD Policy Recommendations. *The Normal Lights*, 17(1).
- Cabillo-Jimenez, M. (2021). Assessment on the Relationship of the Effectiveness of the Gender and Development (GAD) Programs on the Teachers' Attitudes and Perceptions Concerning Gender-Related Issues: A Proposed Action Plan. *Assessment*, 12(23).
- Cagang, A. J. (2023). Gender and Development Towards Gender-sensitive Pedagogical Practices of Pre-service Teachers Basis for a University GAD Program. *Cagang, AJ, Sinang, A., Butlig, SPQ, & Española, E.(2023). Gender and Development Awareness Towards Gender-sensitive Pedagogical Practices of Pre-service Teachers: Basis for a University GAD Program. Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 49(3), 266-280.
- Daniel, W. W., & Cross, C. L. (2018). *Biostatistics: a foundation for analysis in the health sciences*. Wiley.
- Hemillan-Sacro, J., Bauyot, B., & Villegas, J. (2022). Gender mainstreaming in basic education of the City of Mati, Southern Mindanao, Philippines. *Davao Research Journal*, 13(1), 30-49.
- Pedrajas, R. P., & Jalandoni, N. D. (2023). Promoting gender equality in the classroom: Teachers' challenges and strategies. *JETT*, 14(3), 390-398.

- Regalado, M. (2017). Career mobility and gender: A descriptive study of selected deped teachers in Iligan City. *S. Aimimtham & A. Nurmandi, The Complexity of Managing Local Government in Selected ASEAN Countries.*
- Talon, R., Carreon, J., & Diragen, G. (2020). A phenomenological inquiry of gender and development in the classroom program.
- Villagrancia, C. (2023). Assessment on the Implementation of Gender and Development Program at San Francisco Elementary School. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal, 10(5), 553-558.*
- Villanueva, L. C. B. . . (2019). Gender and Development (GAD) Awareness and Perception Survey questionnaire. *Isabelastateuniversityis.*
https://www.academia.edu/40621979/Gender_and_Development_GAD_Awareness_and_Perception_Survey_Questionnaire